

The 7 Best Ayurvedic Beauty Tricks for Your Skin Type

Beauty Tricks From Ayurveda For Your Skin Type

- Understand your Dosha.
- Dosha's Guide to Skincare
- Seasons to Take Into Account
- Use coconut oil to moisturize
- Use raw milk to soothe the body
- Engage in oil pulling.
- Treatment Options

Ayurveda is a well-known method of increasing beauty from the inside out and offers a variety of cosmetic advantages. Discover seven Ayurvedic beauty secrets tailored to your skin type by reading the blog. Ayurveda is a traditional holistic medical system noted for its beauty advantages. Indian women swear by it for its beauty secrets and it has its roots in India dating back thousands of years. According to the [Ayurvedic treatment for Psoriasis](#) concept, internal healing is necessary before you can obtain the ideal level of exterior attractiveness.

Ayurveda bestows you with the treasures of excellent health and, of course, the beautiful beauty secrets through a balanced approach to health, diet, lifestyle, and herbal remedies. Take advantage of the comprehensive Panchakarma Treatment in Kerala, India, to reap the benefits of beauty in the place of origin.

The methods of Ayurveda classify people according to their Dosha, or body constitution, which includes Vata, Pitta, and Kapha. These five elements—air, water, earth, ether, and fire—have uniquely combined to form these doshas.

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Here are the seven Ayurvedic beauty tips that are specific to your skin type for glowing, healthy skin.

Understand your Dosha.

Your skin type is likewise influenced by your body dosha, and Ayurveda treats it similarly while taking your body's constitution into account. Every person has a distinct prakruti at birth. A specific dosha is present when we are born, but throughout time, due to various events, the dosha may get out of balance. Every person is born with two near doshas and one dominant dosha; the third dosha is either the weaker one or has no bearing on the body type.

2. Dosha's Guide to Skincare

The best person to speak with in order to understand your body's doshas and then properly care for your skin is an Ayurvedic therapist or practitioner. Skin that has the Vata Dosha is thin, dry, fragile, fine-pored, and prone to wrinkles. Rosacea, breakouts, and rashes are more likely to occur in Pitta-dominant individuals. People who have kapha have thicker, oilier skin that is more prone to eczema, enlarged pores, and acne.

3. Seasons to Take Into Account

Skin problems are greatly influenced by the weather and the changing of the seasons, with the latter being more crucial to take into account. If you have Vata Dosha, balancing Pitta throughout the heat is necessary. Fall is fantastic for Vata people, while Pitta people prefer summer and early autumn. The Kapha season, which begins around March, beckons. Prior to using the Ayurvedic treatment for psoriasis method to heal skin, it is important to take into account how our atmosphere affects our dosha.

4. Use coconut oil to moisturize

Whatever your skin type, using coconut oil on a regular basis will help you achieve glowing, healthy skin thanks to its cooling properties. Clarified butter or ghee, which tends to soothe skin irritation, restore elasticity, and function as an ideal all-natural mask for bright skin, is revered by some women, especially in India. Use it as body lotion or on your face. Additionally, coconut oil is the most effective makeup remover.

5. Use raw milk to soothe the body

Use raw milk to cleanse the body or indulge in a restorative milk bath. Raw milk with full cream or cream content is a fantastic treatment for all skin types since it has a calming and cooling effect. Put a cotton ball into a small dish of raw, cold milk, then wipe your face while you remove your makeup or after washing your face. This serves as a pore cleanser and natural dirt removal. So, nurture your skin with milk, and vegans may do the same with coconut milk

6. Engage in oil pulling.

Cleanse the body using the oil-pulling technique, then cleanse the skin. Always follow your doctor's advice and gargle with coconut or sesame oil for 10 to 15 minutes before throwing up. You may maintain proper oral hygiene in this way, and it's widely believed that oral health greatly affects overall wellness. During the Rishikesh Yoga Teacher Training program, you will learn the approach in great detail.

7. Treatment Options

- To prepare a facial scrub, combine sugar, rose petals, bhringraj, mint, and slippery elm.

- Cleanse your face and skin with natural rose water for a healthy glow.
- Neem oil should be applied directly to spots or pimples using a cotton ball for best effects.
- Aloe Vera is the answer; you can drink the juice or use the gel as a toner or mask on your face.
- For a healthy scalp and thick hair, use Neem oil, Aloe Vera, and coconut oil.
- These efficient beauty tips and treatments are truly beneficial and appropriate for the skin type for longer-lasting effects.